

Yahga, 4 July 1971

David Stronach
BRITISH INSTITUTE of
PERSIAN STUDIES

Dear David,

When you showed me your letter to
Andrew Williams concerning the problems
at Bushme, it did not register with
me that Andrew did not know that
I was coming to Tehran. He therefore
could not have known to send a note with
me for you. Andrew took Karl and
myself only as far as Sirjan; it was not
decided that I should even consider
going to Tehran until Karl and I were
in Kerman.

I hope that this clears up any
misunderstandings at this point

Sincerely
Richard H. Meade

By hand: Andrew Williamson

BIPS

David Stenard

I was coming to Teton. The day before
could not have been to send a note out
we for you. Andrew took that and
myself only a few to dinner; it was not
decided that I should see you
going to Teton with Karl and I were
a Kerman

I hope the day clears up and
we can be out on the boat

Andrew Williamson